

Deliverable 6.4

Hands-on resources for public engagement events

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1. Introduction

This deliverable D6.4 “Hands-on resources for public engagement events” describes the materials and resources available for consortium members to represent SciRoc and the European Robotics League (ERL) in public engagement events such as conferences, fairs and outreach activities. We have divided the hands-on resources in two different categories: conference events and outreach activities, as they target different audiences.

2. Conference events

This section describes the marketing resources available to consortium partners for promoting the European Robotics League (ERL) and SciRoc H2020 project within the robotics community and the general public in conferences, forums, fairs, exhibitions and local tournaments.

2.1 Marketing resources

The current ERL marketing material comply with the ERL branding guidelines from previous ROCKEU2 Horizon 2020 project and thus, shares the aesthetic design of euRobotics (EUROBOTICS) and SPARC Robotics materials. This is to make the ERL brand stronger in front of the robotics community and to facilitate the use of the materials in conjunction with others from euRobotics (e.g. the European Robotics Forum, European Robotics Week, etc.).

The Open University has designed a specific logo and a brochure to promote the SciRoc project and the 1st SciRoc Challenge. The SciRoc logo and the smart city images have been incorporated in the ERL materials.

All the marketing materials listed in this section comply with the EC guidelines for dissemination and the use of the EU emblem.

2.1.1 Trifold Leaflet

Reusing the design of the ERL trifold-leaflet designed by euRobotics under ROCKEU2 project, we updated the content in line with the SciRoc project and printed the leaflet for distribution at the European Robotics Forum (ERF 2018) in Tampere, Finland, in March 2018. This version of the leaflet is shown in Figure 1.

SPARC Partnership

The EU has been funding research in robotics since 2004, helping Europe to become a world leader in this field.

Under the H2020 SPARC robotics work programme, the European Commission is supporting the European Robotics League.

SPARC enables a coalition of key partners from academia and industry to define the rules for ERL and organise the training workshops and competitions.

More details and information about the European Robotics League at www.robotics-league.eu

Contact us at info@robotics-league.eu

Brought to you by

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under grant agreement no. 78008.

European Robotics League (ERL)

The ERL is a pan-European robotics competition launched under the umbrella of SPARC - the Partnership for Robotics in Europe.

International teams will compete against each other in three vibrant fields of robotics: industrial, service and emergency robotics. Competitors will engage in annual local tournaments organised by a coalition of Europe's most prestigious robotics institutes.

Biennial major tournaments will be held in Smart Cities across Europe, where robots will interact with the smart infrastructure in familiar urban settings.

What ERL stands for...

- ▶ To spur innovation and entrepreneurship to both maintain and extend European leadership in robotics;
- ▶ To provide a unique opportunity to test robots on real world challenges in exciting scenarios;
- ▶ To create convincing user stories, that catch the interest of the general public, scientific community, and industry alike;
- ▶ To increase exposure to industrial and business perspectives of how robotics is applied.

Creating a workforce talent pipeline

On top of industrial and research needs, robot competitions meet educational needs and can serve as an excellent platform for developing the skills of future engineers and scientists.

Having robots perform numerous tasks and benchmarks in competing situations and under varying circumstances raises student awareness and understanding of applied research and development problems in robotics.

Benchmarking in industrially and socially relevant fields

The European Robotics League offers a common framework for four competitions in the fields of Service Robots, Emergency Robots, Industrial Robots and Smart Cities, which pose a range of open societal, scientific, and industrial challenges.

Benchmarking enables teams to compare their robots' performance. This open sharing of data lets developers focus on the approaches that work best.

ERL Industrial Robots

The aim of the league is to foster innovation in industrial robotics. The focus is on manipulation, handling, assembly and transport of pieces and products.

ERL Service Robots

The challenges in the field of service robotics for home are designed around the idea of supporting people in their everyday life.

ERL Emergency Robots

The challenges aim at field robots from ground, aerial and marine domains supporting first responders in emergency situations.

ERL Smart City Challenge

Smart Cities have data infrastructure to support innovation, to become more liveable, resilient and adaptive. In this challenge, industrial, emergency and service robots will interact with the smart urban infrastructure to achieve their tasks.

Figure 1. First version of ERL trifold leaflet. (Photo Credits: ERL)

After the SciRoc consortium decision to change the names of the ERL leagues to better align with the SciRoc Challenge Episodes, we redesigned the leaflet with new content and pictures. We distributed the new leaflet (see Figure 2) at 2018 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS 2018) in Madrid, Spain.

Consortium

The European Robotics League is run by the SciRoc Horizon 2020 project. The SciRoc consortium is led by the University of the West of England, Bristol, and includes ten partners:

- ✦ Centre for Advanced Aerospace Technologies (CAATEC) (Spain)
- ✦ NATO Centre for Maritime Research and Experimentation (CMRE) (Italy)
- ✦ Eurobotics AISBL (Belgium)
- ✦ Association of Instituto Superior Técnico for Research and Development (IST-ID)(Portugal)
- ✦ The Open University (United Kingdom)
- ✦ Politecnico di Milano (Italy)
- ✦ Sapienza University (Italy)
- ✦ University of Applied Sciences Bonn-Rhein-Sieg (Germany)
- ✦ Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (Spain)
- ✦ University of the West of England, Bristol (United Kingdom)

More details and information about the European Robotics League at www.robotics-league.eu

Contact us at info@robotics-league.eu

@ERLrobotleague

European Robotics League

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 780086.

EUROPEAN ROBOTICS LEAGUE

Brought to you by SPARC

www.robotics-league.eu

European Robotics League (ERL)

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- ▶ To provide a unique opportunity to test robots on real world challenges in exciting scenarios;
- ▶ To increase exposure to industrial and business perspectives of how robotics is applied.

Creating a workforce talent pipeline

On top of industrial and research needs, robot competitions meet educational needs and can serve as an excellent platform for developing the skills of students, engineers and scientists.

Having robots perform numerous tasks and under varying circumstances raises awareness and understanding of applied research and development problems in robotics.

Benchmarking in industrially and socially relevant fields

The European Robotics League offers a common framework for four competitions in the fields of Consumer Service Robots, Professional Service Robots, Emergency Service Robots and Smart Cities, which pose a range of open societal, scientific, and industrial challenges.

Benchmarking enables teams to compare their robots' performance. This open sharing of data lets developers focus on the approaches that work best.

ERL Professional Service Robots

The aim of the league is to foster innovation in industrial robotics. The focus is on manipulation, handling, assembly and transport of pieces and products.

ERL Consumer Service Robots

The challenges in the field of service robotics for home are designed around the idea of supporting people in their everyday life.

ERL Emergency Service Robots

The challenges aim at field robots from ground, aerial and marine domains supporting first responders in emergency situations.

ERL Smart Cities Robotics Challenge

Smart Cities have data infrastructure to support innovation, to become more liveable, resilient and adaptive. In the SciRoc Challenge, professional, consumer and emergency service robots will interact with the smart urban infrastructure to achieve their tasks.

Figure 2. Current ERL leaflet. (Photo Credits: ERL)

The last version of the ERL leaflet is available to download and print from Google Drive:

https://drive.google.com/open?id=1bx181h0kJn_KfK5acemNJYqujMiOFCmd

2.1.2 Single leaflet

A two-sided leaflet is available to use within the ERL trifold leaflet or as a single leaflet. Its versatility allows us to adapt information on the SciRoc Challenge and announce conference workshops at lower cost. The single leaflet designed for IROS 2018 included information on the 1st SciRoc Challenge and the Forum on Competitions programme. (See Figure 3).

UWE Bristol can update the content when requested by consortium partners.

Figure 3. Single leaflet printed for IROS 2018. (Photo Credits: ERL)

The design file for printing this leaflet is available on Google Drive.

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1rkXPLjZ053DfZa43btd-IMoUrO4S4KuF>

2.1.3 SciRoc Brochure

The Open University designed a specific brochure for the Call for Expression of Interest (Eoi) of the 1st SciRoc Challenge. The brochure was distributed in the Forum on Smart City Robot Competitions at IROS 2018. It included a beautifully illustrated comic strip that represented the possible Episodes that could take place in the Milton Keynes competition.

The new ERL Smart Cities challenge will show how robots can integrate in the cities of the future as physical agents living in them. Leveraging the ERL Consumer, ERL Professional and ERL Emergency functionalities, robots will cooperate with the smart city infrastructure and interact with its citizens – assisting customers, providing professional services and supporting during emergency situations.

Important dates

- Expression of interest: Sep 01 – Oct 15, 2018
- Rulebook publication: Dec 15, 2018
- Qualification process: Dec 15, 2018 – Jan 31, 2019
- Notification to teams: Feb 15, 2019
- Registration: Mar 01 – Mar 31, 2019

For any further enquiries: info@sciroc.eu

Partners

The European Robotics League (ERL) is the successor to the RoCkIt!, euRathlon and EuRoC robotics competitions, and is now run by the SciRoc EU-Horizon 2020 project under the coordination of University of West of England, Bristol. The ERL comprises annual competitions for Consumer, Professional and Emergency Service Robots, and a biennial robotics challenge for Smart Cities.

The European Robotics League (ERL) Smart Cities presents

The SciRoc Challenge

(The 1st ERL Smart Cities Robotics Challenge)

16 – 22 September 2019

The Centre:MK, Milton Keynes, United Kingdom

www.sciroc.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 780366.

Which episode do you like? Choose online by October 15th

To submit your expression of interest visit: sciroc.eu/expression-of-interest/

Figure 4. SciRoc brochure distributed at IROS 2018. (Photo Credits: ERL)

2.1.4 Lanyard

We have designed a lanyard for staff and teams participating at ERL tournaments (Figure 5). UWE Bristol will provide lanyards to ERL local tournament organisers under request.

Figure 5. ERL-SciRoc-SPARC lanyard. (Photo Credits: ERL)

The design files for printing lanyards is available on Google Drive:

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=14ydpYUaMqci6x-tTkFj6BLnGGYRuz8Rz>

2.1.5 Tote Bag

An ERL tote bag is available as part of the welcome kit given to teams participating at ERL tournaments. The tote bag is common to all the three leagues and includes the logos of the sponsors (depending on the level of sponsorship) of that specific ERL Season. Figure 6 shows the tote bag design for the ERL Season 2018/19. A new tote bag will be designed for ERL Season 2019/2020 and the 1st SCIROC Challenge.

UWE Bristol will provide tote bags to ERL tournament organisers upon request.

The design files for printing ERL tote bags are available on Google Drive:

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=144x735GJ20iRueyxK9Xnlonz2iafeBSH>

Figure 6. ERL Tote bag for Season 2018/2019. (Photo Credits: ERL)

2.1.6 Button Badges

Button Badges of the ERL and SciRoc are available for conference/ exhibition events and the welcome kit for teams. The button badges can be distributed in outreach activities to children of secondary school age. We chose a larger badge to show the logos clearly and to be easy to read and recognise from a distance.

Figure 7. ERL and SciRoc button badges. (Photo Credits: ERL)

UWE Bristol will provide button badges to consortium partners upon request.

The design files for printing the button badges are available on Google Drive:

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1ma3cPtatH1Xckppwiih4iyJs8ZTtX2lw>

2.1.7 Stickers

Stickers of the ERL and SciRoc are available for conference/ exhibition events, the welcome kit for teams and for outreach activities. The stickers come in two different sizes and are an attractive merchandise that is low cost and easy to carry to events.

UWE Bristol will provide stickers to consortium partners under request.

The design files for printing the stickers are available on Google Drive:

https://drive.google.com/open?id=162KljwTFXyQ4SgvJ6jd_LmDQQRk2OzMC

Figure 8. ERL stickers. (Photo Credits: ERL)

2.1.8 Roll up banner

The ERL already had a roll up banner designed during the ROCKEU2 H2020 project. We have updated the design with new images and text that better explains the ERL under SCIROC H2020 project.

The new roll up is available on Google Drive for consortium partners to print.

https://drive.google.com/open?id=1lxwJb9BiD0N44DZDMsK3qhUwKKf_PBT1

(Note: consortium partners can use the old ERL roll up if they still do not have the new one).

Figure 9. (Left) Old ERL banner (Right) New ERL-SCIROC banner. (Photo Credits: ERL)

2.1.9 Presentation Template

A Power Point (PPT) presentation template is available on Google Drive for consortium members to use in conferences and seminars.

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1ODo68F4k7cL0pC2jpOD3bpBwSgPN6nVn>

[TITLE PRESENTATION] [Name, Surname]
[Beneficiary]
[Location], [Date]

Figure 10. ERL presentation template. (Photo Credits: ERL)

2.1.10 Videos

A video illustrating the three ERL leagues and the SciRoc Challenge is available for promoting the Milton Keynes event. We edited a shorter version featuring only the TIAGo robot as requested by PAL Robotics (Platinum Sponsor of the ERL Consumer League) so they could show it in their booth at IROS 2018 and their social media.

The two videos are available on the ERL YouTube channel and Google Drive:

- SciRoc promo video (full version): <https://youtu.be/63Wvm5jE0vE>
- SciRoc promo video (short version featuring TIAGo): <https://youtu.be/O9yHi-xXFEY>
- Google Drive folder: https://drive.google.com/open?id=14XY03I9LA-1qxfJGid5JEqKI9EI3_W-8

Figure 11. Image of the SciRoc promo video. (Photo Credits: ERL)

3. Outreach activities

This section describes the basic setup of an outreach activity that is suitable for a variety of events, like school sessions or science fairs. The purpose of the activity is to establish a conversation with visitors/participants that leads to explaining the European Robotics League in the wider context of robotics research and innovation. Depending on availability, any member of the consortium who would like to deliver the activity can make use of a different set of resources they have available in their institution. Here we will outline the outreach activity as piloted in a school in Thornbury, near Bristol, UK, in February 2018.

3.1 Outreach resources

- Toy robots, ideally ranging from very simple ones (that are obviously not a robot, like a pencil sharpener) to one that could actually be considered a robot, such as Robosapien, Pleo or a custom made educational robot, as used here:

Robosapien by WowWee

Pleo by Innvo Labs

Figure 12. (Left) Robosapiens X. (Photo credit¹: WowWee). (Right) Pleo robot. (Photo Credit²: [Jiuguang Wang](https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pleo#/media/File:Pleo_robot.jpg))

1

<https://wowwee.com/robosapien-x>

2

https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pleo#/media/File:Pleo_robot.jpg

Figure 13. (Left) Robot-shaped pencil sharpener (right) educational robot by Dawn Robotics. (Photo Credit: JohnCraig.co.uk)

- A computer + screen, with a playlist of videos from the web showing different types of robots, from currently used ones like the vacuum cleaner or driverless cars, to search and rescue robots (e.g. videos from euRathlon or ERL Emergency), to popular robots like Paro, the football playing robots, commercial robots (e.g. Pepper, NAO, TIAGo, ANYmal, etc.), and robots from movies. There are a myriads of videos available online, but on request, we can provide a basic set of clips that are suitable for the activity and targeted audience.

Name
🚩 100 Years of Robots in the Movies
🚩 Best goals of RoboCup 2016
🚩 Best Robots in Movies
🚩 BigDog Overview (Updated March 2010)
🚩 Cheetah Robot runs 28.3 mph; a bit faster than Usain Bolt
🚩 euRathlon 2013 - Day 1
🚩 euRathlon 2013 - Day 2
🚩 euRathlon 2013 - Day 3
🚩 euRathlon 2013 - Day 4
🚩 euRathlon 2015 Challenge (video resume)
🚩 EURATHLON 2015
🚩 euRathlon Day 5
🚩 Every Movie Robot SUPERCUT _ Jonathan Mann _ Song A Day _2057

Figure 14. Example of videos included in a playlist.

- A banner to display the European Robotics League branding, ideally with pictures of typical ERL robots, like drones, underwater robots, consumer and professional robots. See in Figure 9 the existing ERL banners that are available to use in the activity.
- Other necessary equipment, like spare batteries, extension cables, chargers, plug adaptors, etc.

Depending on the room and furniture available, the set up can be different. See in Figure 15 an example of a setup (with low tables) for primary school children.

Figure 15. Example of a set up in primary school classroom. (Photo Credits: ERL)

3.2 Delivery

The delivery of this activity is very flexible and hence adaptable to many circumstances. The following is an example as delivered in a science fair at St Mary School in Thornbury, UK, where pupils would attend on a Saturday morning with parents/carers, friends and relatives.

- The banner is set up in a clearly visible position within reach of delivery staff so they can point to the images when necessary.
- The videos from the playlist are running in a loop on the screen.

- Children are allowed to play with the toy robots. The more delicate educational robot can be demonstrated without leaving it in the hands of visitors.

The presenter establishes conversation with the participants, explaining that he/she is there because he/she is very interested in hearing everyone's opinion on what robots are. It has to be stated very quickly that there are no right and wrong answers, as not even the researchers fully agree on what defines a robot. Using the toy and educational robots as examples, as well as those on the video screen and the pictures on the banner, the presenter can gradually steer the conversation. The starting point can be to ask whether one simple robot toy (e.g. a pencil sharpener shaped as a robot) is a robot, everyone agreeing that it is not. Then the questions can point towards the other end of the spectrum, asking whether the educational robot or those seen on the screen, like Pepper, TIAGo or ANYmal, are real robots, where all will agree they are. So what is the difference, what makes the latter a robot, while the pencil sharpener is clearly not one?

Answers will be very varied and expressed in many different ways. The presenter will be able to interpret whether they are referring to autonomy, the ability to do things humans cannot do, the presence of electronics or computers, sensory devices, etc...

At some point in the conversation it can be discussed how robots are already in use in many areas of our everyday lives, but we cease to call them robots and instead call them by ordinary names like "roomba", "driverless car", etc.... The corresponding videos can then be jumped to on the playlist of the computer.

The point of the conversation is not to settle the question of what a robot is but to show that it is an open question, that a lot of research is going on and that initiatives like the European Robotics League is one example of the effort by the robotics community to advance the field by providing scenarios that will allow to put robots to the test in controlled but realistic conditions, and to establish benchmarks to assess the advancement of robotic solutions.

For the adult visitors one can go into more detail about the problem of benchmarking and how this is an important area of research that competitions like ERL are addressing.

3.3 Use for research

With the appropriate ethics clearance from UWE (which has been approved for Deliverable 6.3 ‘public perceptions and attitudes on robotics’ toolkit) and, if necessary, from any local organisation involved, the responses of the visitors can be used as part of research towards public perceptions on robotics. To this end, at the beginning of the activity the presenter has to say explicitly he/she intends to use the answers for such research, and refer to displayed notes where participants are given the option not to interact with the presenter if they do not want their answers or those by minors in their care included in the study. This does not have to become a very formal step, as this may spoil the conversational mood and stop people from participating just because it looks too formal. The displayed note needs to mention that full anonymity is guaranteed, as no personal information is collected (other than a rough estimate of the age bracket of the respondents and their gender, which cannot be used to identify individuals).

For this purpose of research, the presenter will discreetly take notes during or after each conversation, taking a tally of the type of spontaneous responses from the public, regarding what defines a robot. As an orientative example, Appendix 1 lists the word categories or clusters that emerged during the pilot event.

In summary, depending on the purpose of the outreach activity there are two delivery options:

- a) Research purpose: the activity must have the appropriate ethics clearance by the institution gathering the research data and the local organiser (this last one only if needed). Detailed information on the evaluation is available in Deliverable 6.3 “public perceptions and attitudes on robotics” toolkit. To make sure the data gathered can be combined and thematically analysed towards a research paper on public perceptions on robotics for a science communication journal, please contact Dr Hanna Little at info@robotics-league.eu
- b) Public engagement (with no research purpose): follow the information in this document and the one provided by your institution and/or local organiser regarding outreach activities.

Appendix 1

Word categories and clusters that emerged from conversations with the public attending the pilot event

- **What makes you say that a specific item is a robot?**

Autonomy I
Has a switch

Self powered II (except batteries ?)

Motion II

Don't know I

Moves

Uses oxygen

↓

Control

Control + mechanical parts

↓

Do things on their own

Circuits + mechanical parts

Power

Remote controlled

Has a computer inside
+ moves

Electronics + looks like human

Electronics + do things

Has cables and circuits IIIII

Control + do things on its own

Has eyes
+ "do things"

Control/programming II
+ self powered

Notes:

↓ means one concept led to the other during a conversation

+ means concepts were mentioned together right away

Looks like humans IIII